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October 28, 2022

Abstract. The mean energy in hypothetical thermodynamic systems is evaluated. All of these systems possess only the so-called internal energy but not free energy. Each evaluated system has an infinite number of states with different levels of energy (E_i), and all two-consecutive energy levels, E_{i+1} and E_i , are separated by the same amount of energy (ΔE). Three examples of such a type of system with different E_0 are evaluated, a level of energy that is defined as the lowest non-real-zero level, and is specified here as equaling $\frac{1}{2}\Delta E$, $2\Delta E$, or ΔE itself. Given that the systems have no free energy, the partition function $Z = 1$. Under this condition, the systems are such partitioned that the probability p_i of state i is given by $\frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}}$, $\frac{1}{\varphi^{i+2}}$, or $\frac{1}{2^{i+1}}$, in which φ is the geometric-constant golden-ratio. When the mean energy of the system is evaluated as the sum of the weighted energy of individual states, effectively in the form of the Gibbs entropy, the evaluation yields $\frac{1}{\beta}(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi})\ln\varphi$, $\frac{1}{\beta}\varphi(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi})\ln\varphi$, or $\frac{1}{\beta}2\ln 2$, in which thermodynamic $\beta = \frac{1}{k_B T}$, i.e., the inverse of the product of the Boltzmann constant k_B and the absolute temperature T in the unit K . Thus, a fundamental difference among the three examples is that two of them are expressed with the irrational number φ whereas the remaining one is expressed with the integer number 2.

Introduction

The hypothetical thermodynamic systems considered here have only internal energy but not any free energy, i.e., the partition function $Z = 1$. Each system possesses an infinite number of states with different levels of energy (E_i ; $i = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots$). All pairs of consecutive energy levels, E_{i+1} and E_i , have the same spacing (ΔE). The lowest level of energy (E_0), which is not real zero, differs among the systems. In the three examples of this type of system evaluated below, E_0 is specified as equaling $\frac{1}{2}\Delta E$, $2\Delta E$, or ΔE itself.

Evaluation of hypothetical systems

In the first evaluated system where $E_0 = \frac{1}{2}\Delta E$, the individual energy levels are expressed as

$$E_i = (2i + 1)E_0 \quad (1)$$

which formulaically resembles the energy eigenvalues for the solution of the time-independent Schrödinger equation for a quantum harmonic oscillator [1]. In accordance with the Maxwell-

Boltzmann statistics, the relation between the energy level E_0 of the system, as defined by Eq. 1, and the probability p_0 of the corresponding state is given by

$$E_0 = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln Z p_0 = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln \frac{Z}{x} = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln \frac{1}{x} \quad (2)$$

where $Z = 1$, as specified above, the thermodynamic $\beta = \frac{1}{k_B T}$, i.e., the inverse of the product of the Boltzmann constant k_B and the absolute temperature T in the unit K , and p_0 is defined as

$$p_0 = \frac{1}{x}. \quad (3)$$

Then, the general relation between E_i and p_i for state i may be written as

$$E_i = (2i + 1)E_0 = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln Z p_i = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln \frac{Z}{x^{2i+1}} = -\frac{1}{\beta} \ln \frac{1}{x^{2i+1}} \quad (4)$$

where

$$p_i = \frac{1}{x^{2i+1}} \quad (5)$$

and then

$$\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} p_i = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x^{2i+1}} = 1 \quad (6)$$

which, for ease of derivation, is replaced by

$$\frac{1}{x} + \frac{1}{x^3} + \frac{1}{x^5} + \frac{1}{x^7} + \frac{1}{x^9} + \dots + \frac{1}{x^{2m-1}} + \frac{1}{x^{2m+1}} = 1. \quad (7)$$

After being multiplied by $\frac{1}{x^2}$, Eq. 7 becomes

$$\frac{1}{x^3} + \frac{1}{x^5} + \frac{1}{x^7} + \frac{1}{x^9} + \frac{1}{x^{11}} + \dots + \frac{1}{x^{2m+1}} + \frac{1}{x^{2m+3}} = \frac{1}{x^2}. \quad (8)$$

A subtraction of Eq. 8 from Eq. 7 yields

$$\frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x^{2m+3}} = 1 - \frac{1}{x^2}. \quad (9)$$

When $m \rightarrow \infty$, $\frac{1}{x^{2m+3}} \rightarrow 0$, and Eq. 9 approaches

$$\frac{1}{x} = 1 - \frac{1}{x^2} \quad (10)$$

rearranged to

$$x^2 - x - 1 = 0 \quad (11)$$

which corresponds to the quadratic equation for solving the geometric-constant golden-ratio φ , and whose solutions are

$$x = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2} = \varphi \quad (12)$$

The positive solution is the non-transcendental, irrational number 1.618..., and is adopted here.

Substituting φ into Eq. 5 yields

$$p_i = \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}}. \quad (13)$$

This function is self-normalized in the following infinite geometric series

$$\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} = 1 \quad (14)$$

which may be used to define a partitioned probability space (Fig. 1A).

Fig. 1. (A and B) Shown is one face of a unit cube. Partitions I and J in the shown unit-square face are drawn according to Eqs. 14 and 17, respectively. The extra maroon lines in B indicate the extra partitions beyond those in A. The small grey square in A or B can be further partitioned infinitely, following the rules set by Eqs. 14 or 17. The cube is partitioned only in the two dimensions shown in the page but not in the third dimension perpendicular to the page.

The average energy U of the system may be calculated as the sum of the weighted energy of individual states, effectively in the form of the Gibbs entropy:

$$U = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} p_i \ln p_i = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} = \frac{1}{\beta} \left(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi} \right) \ln \varphi = \frac{1}{\beta} \sqrt{5} \ln \varphi \quad (15)$$

(see Appendix I for detailed operations).

Furthermore, according to the well-known relation

$$\frac{1}{\varphi^i} = \frac{1}{\varphi^{i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{i+2}} \quad (16)$$

a further partition of each term in Eq. 14 by a ratio of φ would lead to another type of partitioned probability space (Fig. 1B), which is defined by

$$\sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} = 1. \quad (17)$$

This latter partition (J) would correspond to a second system where $E_0 = 2\Delta E$. The mean energy U of this further partitioned system may be calculated as

$$U = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} p_j \ln p_j = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} = \frac{1}{\beta} (\varphi^2 + 1) \ln \varphi = \frac{1}{\beta} \varphi \left(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi} \right) \ln \varphi = \frac{1}{\beta} \varphi \sqrt{5} \ln \varphi \quad (18)$$

(see Appendix II for detailed operations). Eq. 18 differs from Eq. 15 by a ratio of φ .

In light that partition I corresponds to the system where $E_0 = \frac{1}{2}\Delta E$ and partition J corresponds to the system where $E_0 = 2\Delta E$, one may wonder what the partitioned probability space, which corresponds to $E_0 = \Delta E$, might be. In a general term of probability, this latter partition may be expressed initially as

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_k = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{y^{k+1}} = 1. \quad (19)$$

For ease of derivation, Eq. 19 is replaced by

$$\frac{1}{y} + \frac{1}{y^2} + \frac{1}{y^3} + \frac{1}{y^4} + \frac{1}{y^5} + \dots + \frac{1}{y^m} + \frac{1}{y^{m+1}} = 1. \quad (20)$$

After being multiplied by $\frac{1}{y}$, Eq. 20 becomes

$$\frac{1}{y^2} + \frac{1}{y^3} + \frac{1}{y^4} + \frac{1}{y^5} + \frac{1}{y^6} + \dots + \frac{1}{y^{m+1}} + \frac{1}{y^{m+2}} = \frac{1}{y}. \quad (21)$$

A subtraction of Eq. 21 from Eq. 20 yields

$$\frac{1}{y} - \frac{1}{y^{m+2}} = 1 - \frac{1}{y}. \quad (22)$$

When $m \rightarrow \infty$, $\frac{1}{y^{m+2}} \rightarrow 0$, and Eq. 22 approaches

$$\frac{1}{y} = 1 - \frac{1}{y} \quad (23)$$

rearranged to

$$y = 2. \quad (24)$$

Substituting Eq. 24 into Eq. 19 yields

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} = 1 \quad (25)$$

which is a well-known geometry series that is also self-normalized and thus describes a third partitioned probability space here. The mean energy U of such a partitioned system may be calculated as

$$U = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} p_k \ln p_k = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} \ln \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} = \frac{1}{\beta} 2 \ln 2 = \frac{1}{\beta} \ln 4 \quad (26)$$

(see Appendix III for detailed operations).

Note that mathematically, as a well known series representation, $\ln 2$ may be expressed as

$$\ln 2 = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n 2^n} \quad (27)$$

whereas $\ln \varphi$ may be expressed as [2]:

$$\ln \varphi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n \varphi^{2n}} \quad (28)$$

or

$$\ln \varphi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2n \varphi^n} \quad (29)$$

(for Eq. 29 see Appendix IV).

Discussion

Partitions I and J are both φ -based systems, the latter of which may be perceived as a result of a further partition of the former by a ratio of φ . Furthermore, the entropy of the former system differs from that of the latter system also by a ratio of φ (Eqs. 15 and 18). In contrast, the third evaluated partitioned system is a 2-based one. Given 2 is an integer number and φ is an irrational number, the value of entropy of the system defined by the third partition (Eq. 26) could not be perfectly related to that defined by partition I or J (Eqs. 15 and 18). Nonetheless, the amount of mean energy U of the former system might, in theory, be perfectly related to those of the latter systems, if the value of its temperature were expressed in a compatible form that contains φ .

The entropy and mean energy U of both φ -based systems may, however, be readily related to that of a previously evaluated two-state system [3]. The energy of one of the two states is twice as much as that of the other, i.e.,

$$E_2 = 2E_1. \quad (30)$$

The probabilities of the two states are given by

$$p_1 = \frac{1}{\varphi} \quad (31)$$

and

$$p_2 = \frac{1}{\varphi^2}. \quad (32)$$

Thus, p_1 and p_2 define the probabilities of two portions in a space partitioned by φ , whose summation is given by

$$\sum_{l=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi_l} = 1. \quad (33)$$

The average energy U of this two-state system may be expressed as

$$U = -\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{l=1}^{N=2} p_l \ln p_l = -\frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) = \frac{1}{\beta} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi \quad (34)$$

Furthermore, the following apparent relation is reached there [3]:

$$-\frac{1}{\beta} \sum_{l=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi_l} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi J = \frac{1}{2} (G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1}) \quad (35)$$

where G and h are the Newtonian gravitational constant and the Planck constant, respectively, whose exact values used to derive this relation are given in the references 4-6.

It is noteworthy that the two partitioned systems defined by Eqs 14 and 33 are related such that a further partition of the second term $\frac{1}{\varphi^2}$ in Eq. 33, in accordance with $\sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2l+1}}$, would convert Eq. 33 to Eq. 14. Furthermore, under the condition that β is the same in Eqs. 15, 18, and 35, relating them yields

$$-\frac{1}{\varphi^2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} = -\frac{1}{\varphi} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} = -\sum_{l=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi_l} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi \quad (36)$$

and then

$$-\frac{1}{\varphi^2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} J = -\frac{1}{\varphi} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} J = \frac{1}{2} (G \times 10^{10} \text{ kg}^2 \text{ m}^{-1} + h \times 10^{33} \text{ s}^{-1}) \quad (37)$$

In another previous study [7], the following two related, apparent relations were reached:

$$\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{Gc^2}{k_e} \times 10^3 \frac{s^2 \text{ kg}^2}{\text{m}^2 \text{ C}^2} + h \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2} \right) = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi = -\sum_{l=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \quad (38)$$

and furthermore

$$\frac{\pi Gcqe^2}{\alpha h} \times 10^3 \frac{s^2 \text{ kg}^2}{\text{m}^2 \text{ C}^2} + \frac{h}{2} \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi = -\sum_{l=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \quad (39)$$

where k_e is the Coulomb constant, c is the speed of light in vacuum, q_e is the elementary charge with the unit C , α is the fine-structure constant. Formulaically, relating Eq. 36 to Eqs. 38 or 39 gives

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{Gc^2}{k_e} \times 10^3 \frac{s^2 kg^2}{m^2 c^2} + h \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2} \right) &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi = - \sum_{l=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \\
&= - \frac{1}{\varphi} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \\
&= - \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} \quad (40)
\end{aligned}$$

or

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2\pi Gc q_e^2}{ah} \times 10^3 \frac{s^2 kg^2}{m^2 c^2} + h \times 10^{33} \frac{s}{kg \cdot m^2} \right) &= \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi = - \sum_{l=1}^{N=2} \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi_l} \\
&= - \frac{1}{\varphi} \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \\
&= - \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}}. \quad (41)
\end{aligned}$$

The first series in Eq. 40 or 41 expresses the sum of weighted natural logarithmic probabilities of the two unequal partitions of a probability space whereas the latter two series express those of infinite, asymmetric partitions in accordance with Eqs. 14 or 17.

Appendix I

As shown below, the compact expression of Eq. 15 can be reached from the following relation:

$$-\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = \left(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi}\right) \ln \varphi = \sqrt{5} \ln \varphi \quad (42)$$

on the basis that

$$-\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \rightarrow -\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \quad (43)$$

when $n \rightarrow \infty$, and $\frac{1}{\varphi^{2n}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \rightarrow 0$.

Let's start by setting

$$-\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2i+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{2n+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} = A1 \quad (44)$$

Then, based on the known feature of φ

$$\frac{1}{\varphi^j} = \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+1}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+2}}; j = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (45)$$

the expression A1 can be propagated as illustrated below:

$$A1 = \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \dots + \frac{2n-5}{\varphi^{2n-5}} + \frac{2n-3}{\varphi^{2n-3}} + \frac{2n-1}{\varphi^{2n-1}} + \frac{2n+1}{\varphi^{2n}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n+1}}\right) \ln \varphi = A2 \quad (46)$$

$$A2 = \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \dots + \frac{2n-5}{\varphi^{2n-5}} + \frac{2n-3}{\varphi^{2n-3}} + \frac{2n-1}{\varphi^{2n-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n+1}}\right) \ln \varphi = A3 \quad (47)$$

$$A3 = \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} \dots + \frac{2n-5}{\varphi^{2n-5}} + \frac{2n-3}{\varphi^{2n-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n+1}}\right) \ln \varphi = A4 \quad (48)$$

$$A4 = \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \dots + \frac{2n-5}{\varphi^{2n-6}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n+1}}\right) \ln \varphi = A5 \quad (49)$$

$$A5 = \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \frac{7}{\varphi^6} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-6}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n+1}}\right) \ln \varphi = A6 \quad (50)$$

$$A6 = \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-6}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n+1}}\right) \ln \varphi = A7 \quad (51)$$

$$A7 = \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-6}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n+1}}\right) \ln \varphi = A8 \quad (52)$$

$$A8 = \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \cdots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-6}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n+1}} \right) \ln\varphi = A9 \quad (53)$$

$$A9 = \left(1 + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \cdots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-6}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-1}} \right) \ln\varphi = A10 \quad (54)$$

$$A10 = \left(1 + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \cdots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-6}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-3}} \right) \ln\varphi = A11 \quad (55)$$

$$A11 = \left(1 + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \cdots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-6}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-5}} \right) \ln\varphi = A12 \quad (56)$$

$$A12 = \left(1 + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \cdots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{2n-7}} \right) \ln\varphi = A13 \quad (57)$$

...

$$A13 = \left(1 + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} \right) \ln\varphi = A14 \quad (58)$$

$$A14 = \left(1 + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} \right) \ln\varphi = A15 \quad (59)$$

$$A15 = \left(1 + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} \right) \ln\varphi = A16 \quad (60)$$

$$A16 = \left(1 + \frac{2}{\varphi} \right) \ln\varphi = \varphi \left(\frac{1}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln\varphi = \varphi \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln\varphi = \left(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi} \right) \ln\varphi = \sqrt{5} \ln\varphi \quad (61)$$

Appendix II

Eq. 18 may be expressed as the sum of two series:

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+1}} = \sum_{j_1=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_1+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_1+1}} + \sum_{j_2=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_2+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_2+1}} \quad (62)$$

where $j_1 = 1,3,5 \dots$ whereas $j_2=2,4,6\dots$ Either series can be evaluated as illustrated in Appendix I. The first of the latter two series in Eq. 62 may be expressed as

$$B1 = -\sum_{j_i=1}^m \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_i+1}} - \left(\frac{1}{\varphi^{m+2}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+3}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+3}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \rightarrow -\sum_{j_i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_i+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_i+1}} \quad (63)$$

On the basis that when $m \rightarrow \infty$, and $\frac{1}{\varphi^{m+2}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+3}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+3}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \rightarrow 0$. The expression $B1$ can be propagated as illustrated below:

$$B1 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{4}{\varphi^4} + \frac{6}{\varphi^6} + \dots + \frac{m-3}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{m-1}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{m+1}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{m+3}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+3}} \right) \ln \varphi = B2 \quad (64)$$

$$B2 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{4}{\varphi^4} + \frac{6}{\varphi^6} + \dots + \frac{m-3}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{m-1}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{m+1}{\varphi^m} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+3}} \right) \ln \varphi = B3 \quad (65)$$

$$B3 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{4}{\varphi^4} + \frac{6}{\varphi^6} + \dots + \frac{m-3}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{m-1}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^m} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+3}} \right) \ln \varphi = B4 \quad (66)$$

$$B4 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{4}{\varphi^4} + \frac{6}{\varphi^6} + \dots + \frac{m-3}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^m} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+3}} \right) \ln \varphi = B5 \quad (67)$$

$$B5 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{4}{\varphi^4} + \frac{6}{\varphi^6} + \frac{8}{\varphi^7} \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^m} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+3}} \right) \ln \varphi = B6 \quad (68)$$

$$B6 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{4}{\varphi^4} + \frac{6}{\varphi^5} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^m} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+3}} \right) \ln \varphi = B7 \quad (69)$$

$$B7 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi^2} + \frac{4}{\varphi^3} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^m} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+3}} \right) \ln \varphi = B8 \quad (70)$$

$$B8 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^m} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+3}} \right) \ln \varphi = B9 \quad (71)$$

$$B9 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^m} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+1}} \right) \ln \varphi = B10 \quad (72)$$

$$B9 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-1}} \right) \ln \varphi = B10 \quad (73)$$

$$B10 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-3}} \right) \ln \varphi = B11 \quad (74)$$

$$B11 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-5}} \right) \ln \varphi = B12 \quad (75)$$

...

$$B12 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} + \frac{2}{\varphi^8} \right) \ln \varphi = B13 \quad (76)$$

$$B13 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} \right) \ln \varphi = B14 \quad (77)$$

$$B14 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} \right) \ln \varphi = B15 \quad (78)$$

$$B15 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{2}{\varphi^2} \right) \ln \varphi = B16 \quad (79)$$

$$B16 = 2 \ln \varphi = B17 \quad (80)$$

The second of the latter two series in Eq. 62, in which again $j_2 = 2, 4, 6, \dots$, may be expressed as

$$C1 = -\sum_{j_2=2}^m \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_2+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_2+1}} - \left(\frac{1}{\varphi^{m+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+2}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \right) \rightarrow -\sum_{j_2=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_2+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j_2+1}} \quad (81)$$

on the basis that when $m \rightarrow \infty$, $\frac{1}{\varphi^{m+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+2}} + \frac{1}{\varphi^{m+2}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^2} \rightarrow 0$. The expression C1 can be propagated

as illustrated below:

$$C1 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \frac{7}{\varphi^7} + \dots + \frac{m-4}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{m-2}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{m}{\varphi^m} + \frac{m+2}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} \right) \ln \varphi = C2 \quad (82)$$

$$C2 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \frac{7}{\varphi^7} + \dots + \frac{m-4}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{m-2}{\varphi^{m-2}} + \frac{m}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} \right) \ln \varphi = C3 \quad (83)$$

$$C3 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \frac{7}{\varphi^7} + \dots + \frac{m-4}{\varphi^{m-4}} + \frac{m-2}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} \right) \ln \varphi = C4 \quad (84)$$

$$C4 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \frac{7}{\varphi^7} + \dots + \frac{m-4}{\varphi^{m-5}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} \right) \ln \varphi = C5 \quad (85)$$

$$C5 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \frac{7}{\varphi^7} + \frac{9}{\varphi^8} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-5}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} \right) \ln \varphi = C6 \quad (86)$$

$$C6 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^5} + \frac{7}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^8} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-5}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} \right) \ln \varphi = C7 \quad (87)$$

$$C7 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^3} + \frac{5}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^8} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-5}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} \right) \ln \varphi = C8 \quad (88)$$

$$C8 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^8} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-5}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m+2}} \right) \ln \varphi = C9 \quad (89)$$

$$C9 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^8} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-5}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-1}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^m} \right) \ln \varphi = C10 \quad (90)$$

$$C10 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^8} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-5}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-3}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-2}} \right) \ln \varphi = C11 \quad (91)$$

$$C11 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^8} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-5}} + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-4}} \right) \ln \varphi = C12 \quad (92)$$

$$C12 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^8} + \dots + \frac{2}{\varphi^{m-6}} \right) \ln \varphi = C13 \quad (93)$$

...

$$C13 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^8} + \frac{2}{\varphi^9} \right) \ln \varphi = C14 \quad (94)$$

$$C14 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^6} + \frac{2}{\varphi^7} \right) \ln \varphi = C15 \quad (95)$$

$$C15 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^4} + \frac{2}{\varphi^5} \right) \ln \varphi = C16 \quad (96)$$

$$C16 = \left(\frac{3}{\varphi^2} + \frac{2}{\varphi^3} \right) \ln \varphi = C17 \quad (97)$$

$$C17 = \left(\frac{2}{\varphi} + \frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) \ln\varphi = C18 \quad (98)$$

$$C18 = \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi}\right) \ln\varphi = C19 \quad (99)$$

Combining Eqs. 62, 63, 80, 81 and 99 yields:

$$\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+1}} \ln \frac{1}{\varphi^{j+1}} = B1 + C1 = B17 + C19 = 2\ln\varphi + \left(1 + \frac{1}{\varphi}\right) \ln\varphi = (\varphi^2 + 1)\ln\varphi = \varphi \left(\varphi + \frac{1}{\varphi}\right) \ln\varphi \quad (100)$$

Appendix III

As shown below, the compact expression of Eq. 26 can be reached from the following relation:

$$-\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} \ln \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} + \frac{1}{2^{n+1}} \ln \frac{1}{2^{n+1}} = \ln 4 \quad (101)$$

on the basis that

$$-\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} \ln \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} + \frac{1}{2^{n+1}} \ln \frac{1}{2^{n+1}} \rightarrow -\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} \ln \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} \quad (102)$$

when $n \rightarrow \infty$, and $\frac{1}{2^{n+1}} \ln \frac{1}{2^{n+1}} \rightarrow 0$.

Let's start by setting

$$-\sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} \ln \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} + \frac{1}{2^{n+1}} \ln \frac{1}{2^{n+1}} = D1 \quad (103)$$

which can be propagated as illustrated below:

$$D1 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{4}{2^4} + \frac{5}{2^5} + \dots + \frac{n-1}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{n}{2^n} + \frac{n+1}{2^{n+1}} + \frac{n+1}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D2 \quad (104)$$

$$D2 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{4}{2^4} + \frac{5}{2^5} + \dots + \frac{n-1}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{n}{2^n} + \frac{2n}{2^{n+1}} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D3 \quad (105)$$

$$D3 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{4}{2^4} + \frac{5}{2^5} + \dots + \frac{n-1}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{n}{2^n} + \frac{n}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D4 \quad (106)$$

$$D4 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{4}{2^4} + \frac{5}{2^5} + \dots + \frac{n-1}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{2(n-1)}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D5 \quad (107)$$

$$D5 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{4}{2^4} + \frac{5}{2^5} + \dots + \frac{n-1}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{n-1}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{2}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D6 \quad (108)$$

$$D6 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{4}{2^4} + \frac{5}{2^5} + \dots + \frac{2(n-2)}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{2}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{2}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D7 \quad (109)$$

...

$$D7 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{4}{2^4} + \frac{5}{2^5} + \frac{5}{2^5} \dots + \frac{2}{2^{n-2}} + \frac{2}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{2}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D8 \quad (110)$$

$$D8 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{4}{2^4} + \frac{4}{2^4} + \frac{2}{2^5} \dots + \frac{2}{2^{n-2}} + \frac{2}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{2}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D9 \quad (111)$$

$$D9 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{3}{2^3} + \frac{2}{2^4} + \frac{2}{2^5} \dots + \frac{2}{2^{n-2}} + \frac{2}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{2}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D10 \quad (112)$$

$$D10 = \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{2}{2^3} + \frac{2}{2^4} + \frac{2}{2^5} \dots + \frac{2}{2^{n-2}} + \frac{2}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{2}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D11 \quad (113)$$

$$D11 = \left(\frac{2}{2} + \frac{2}{2^2} + \frac{2}{2^3} + \frac{2}{2^4} + \frac{2}{2^5} \dots + \frac{2}{2^{n-2}} + \frac{2}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{2}{2^n} + \frac{2}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D12 \quad (114)$$

$$D13 = 2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^3} + \frac{1}{2^4} + \frac{1}{2^5} \dots + \frac{1}{2^{n-2}} + \frac{1}{2^{n-1}} + \frac{1}{2^n} + \frac{1}{2^{n+1}} \right) \ln 2 = D14 \quad (115)$$

When $n \rightarrow \infty$, Eq. 115 is reduced to

$$D14 \rightarrow 2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} \ln 2 = 2 \ln 2 = \ln 4 \quad (116)$$

given that $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^{k+1}} = 1$ (Eq. 25).

Appendix IV

The following relation [2],

$$-\ln\left(1 - \frac{1}{\varphi}\right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n\varphi^n} \quad (117)$$

may be re-expressed as

$$-\ln\left(\frac{1}{\varphi^2}\right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n\varphi^n} \quad (118)$$

and then be rearranged to

$$\ln\varphi = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2n\varphi^n}. \quad (119)$$

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